

**METAPHOR AND ITS LINGUISTIC FUNCTIONS IN NEWSPAPER
TEXT**

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Abstract: Metaphor is a linguistic device that can be used to make language more vivid, attractive and informative. It literally works by comparing two dissimilar things. Metaphors can be used in different ways in newspaper texts. They can be used in headlines, subheadings, body text, and even headings. In the following article, we will try to study and research the linguistic stylistic tools used in newspaper texts.

Key words: Metaphor, newspaper, cover, text, analysis, linguistic tool, figurative expression, metonymy, synecdoche, differentiation.

Annotatsiya: Metafora tilni yanada jonli, jozibali va ma'lumotli qilish uchun ishlatilishi mumkin bo'lgan lingvistik vositadir. U tom ma'noda o'xshash bo'lmagan ikkita narsani solishtirish orqali ishlaydi. Gazeta matnlarida metafora turlicha qo'llanilishi mumkin. Ular sarlavhalar, sarlavhalar, asosiy matn va hatto sarlavhalarda ishlatilishi mumkin. Quyidagi maqolada biz gazeta matnlarida foydalaniladigan lingvostilistik vositalarni o'rganib tadqiq qilishga harakat qilib ko'ramiz.

Kalit so'zlar: Metafora, gazeta, muqova, matn, analiz, lingvostilistik vosita, majoziy ifoda, metonomiya, senekdoxa, farqlash.

Аннотация: Метафора – лингвистический прием, с помощью которого можно сделать язык более ярким, привлекательным и информативным. Это буквально работает путем сравнения двух непохожих вещей. Метафоры в газетных текстах могут использоваться по-разному. Их можно использовать в заголовках, подзаголовках, основном тексте и даже заголовках. В следующей статье мы попытаемся изучить и исследовать лингвистические стилистические средства, используемые в газетных текстах.

Ключевые слова: Метафора, газета, обложка, текст, анализ, языковой инструмент, образное выражение, метонимия, синекдоха, дифференциация.

A metaphor is a figure of speech that literally compares two dissimilar things. It is a type of figurative language that allows writers and speakers to create vivid images and concepts in the minds of their listeners.

Metaphors are often used to make comparisons between abstract ideas and concrete objects. For example, someone may say that their love for someone is "like a burning fire." This metaphor compares the abstract idea of love to the concrete object of a burning fire. The speaker emphasizes that their love is as passionate and intense as a burning fire. A metaphor can also be used to compare two things that are usually unrelated. For example, someone might say their boss is a "drill sergeant." This metaphor compares the boss to a sergeant who is a military instructor. The speaker notes that their boss is as strict and demanding as a school sergeant.

Various studies show that metaphor can be used to create a variety of effects, including:

Clarity: Metaphors help clarify complex ideas by making them clearer and easier to understand.

Emotion: A metaphor can evoke a strong emotion in a reader or listener by comparing something abstract with something concrete.

Humor: Metaphors can be used to create humor by comparing two very different things.

Beauty: Metaphors can be used to create beautiful and expressive language.

As noted in various literatures, metaphors are a powerful tool that can be used to make language more effective and interesting. By understanding how metaphors work, writers and speakers can use them to create more powerful and memorable messages. Above, we will try to clarify our point with the example of metaphors that are widely used in today's newspaper texts as a proof of our point.

Some of the most common metaphors used in newspapers are:

War: This metaphor is often used to describe political or economic conflicts. For example, a newspaper article might say "the two countries are locked in a trade war" or "the stock market is at war."

Sports: This metaphor is often used to describe competition or competition. For example, a newspaper article might say "two candidates are neck and neck in the polls" or "two companies are fighting for market dominance."

Health: This metaphor is often used to describe the state of the economy or society. For example, a newspaper article might say "the economy is good" or "social media is a platform for spreading misinformation."

Nature: This metaphor is often used to describe complex or abstract concepts. For example, a newspaper article might say "the law is a jungle" or "the political process is a labyrinth."

These metaphors are used to make news more interesting and engaging and to help readers understand complex concepts. They can also be used to create a certain tone or mood in a news story.

It should be noted that excessive use of some metaphors can lead to rudeness in speech. For example, the "war on drugs" metaphor is now widely used and has lost its initial impact. It is important for journalists to use metaphors sparingly and carefully, to make sure that they are fresh and original.

Some examples of linguistic metaphors that can be used in newspaper texts are:

Personification: This is a metaphor that gives human qualities to non-human things. For example, a newspaper article might say "the stock market rumbled" or "the river danced."

Simile: This is a metaphor that compares two things using the words "like" or "like." For example, a newspaper article might say that the new CEO is a "breath of fresh air" or that the economy is "on the rocks."

Metonymy: A metaphor that replaces one thing with something closely related to it. For example, a newspaper article might say that Wall Street is worried about the economy or that the White House is considering new legislation.

Synecdoche: This is a metaphor that uses a part of something to represent the whole. For example, a newspaper article might say that the "fleet" is preparing for war or that "the masses" are demanding change.

There are a number of potential problems with the use of linguistic devices in newspaper texts. Some of the more common ones include:

Misrepresentation: Linguistic devices can be used to manipulate language and create false or misleading impressions. For example, a newspaper headline might use the word "rise" to describe an average rise in the stock market, or the word "plummet" to describe a simple decline. This can lead readers to misinterpret the true significance of the story being reported.

Based on the results of the research, here are some tips for journalists on responsible and ethical use of linguistic tools:

1. Be aware of the potential for bias and manipulation in the use of language.
2. Use clear, concise and to the point language.
3. Avoid using jargon or technical language that the average reader would not understand.
4. Be respectful of different cultures and viewpoints.
5. Be honest and transparent in your reporting. But in some cases, there may be incorrect metaphors that can be used in newspaper texts.

Examples of metaphorical expressions that can be used in newspaper texts:

Political metaphors: "The government is at a crossroads", "The president is fighting an uphill battle", "The two parties are deadlocked".

Economic metaphors: "The stock market is in play", "The economy is in trouble", "The government is pouring money into the economy".

Social metaphors: "Crime is a cancer in society", "Education is the key to success", "Internet is a double-edged sword".

Environmental metaphors: "Climate change is a ticking time bomb," "The planet is choking on pollution," "We're all in the same boat."

It is important that journalists do not use inappropriate metaphors in their writing. The wrong metaphor can make newspaper texts confusing, misleading, and even offensive. Instead, journalists should use clear, concise, accurate, metaphors that match the tone and theme of the text. By following these tips, journalists can use linguistic tools to inform and engage their readers without misleading or manipulating them.

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